

CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL FEATURES OF TRIGEMINAL NEURALGIA AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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Abstract. *Currently, peripheral nerve diseases have become among the most relevant medical issues. Among them, trigeminal neuralgia is one of the most common disorders of the peripheral nervous system. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate patients suffering from trigeminal neuralgia (TN). For this purpose, a study was conducted on 200 patients aged 17 to 70 years diagnosed with trigeminal neuralgia who were examined by a neurologist at the Jondor District Multidisciplinary Central Polyclinic. In the study population, 52 patients (26%) were male and 148 patients (74%) were female.*

Keywords: *trigeminal neuralgia, pain syndrome, sensory disturbances.*

Introduction. The intensity of pain during attacks of trigeminal neuralgia has attracted considerable scientific interest, as it is associated with physiological protective mechanisms formed in the central nervous system. This factor plays an important role in selecting the most effective treatment strategies [5,6].

The prevalence of trigeminal neuralgia is estimated at approximately 15 cases per 1,000 population. The disease most commonly occurs in middle age, particularly between 40 and 50 years, and is more frequently observed in women [7,8]. According to the 10th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10), trigeminal nerve lesions are classified as “trigeminal neuralgia” (paroxysmal facial pain syndrome), “atypical facial pain,” “other trigeminal nerve disorders,” and “unspecified trigeminal nerve disorders.” The International Headache Society classifies trigeminal neuralgia within the group of cranial neuralgias, pain due to nerve trunk lesions, deafferentation pain, idiopathic and symptomatic facial pain, as well as other types of facial pain [1,2,5].

Due to the progressive course of the disease and resistance to physiotherapeutic and reflexotherapy treatment, surgical interventions are also applied in patients with trigeminal neuralgia. The pathogenesis of the disease is explained by several theories; however, in most cases, the most reliable cause is intra- or extracranial compression of the trigeminal nerve. This compression may result from space-occupying lesions of the posterior cranial fossa (acoustic neuroma, meningioma, pontine glioma), displacement or dilation of cerebellar arteries, basilar artery aneurysm, tunnel syndrome (compression of the second and third branches, congenital narrowing of bony canals in the supraorbital fissure or mandible, and age-related vascular pathology), as well as odontogenic or rhinogenic inflammatory processes. The disease may also develop after tooth extraction, odontogenic neuralgia, cerebrovascular disorders of the brainstem, herpes infection, or, more rarely, due to demyelination of the trigeminal nerve sheath in multiple sclerosis [3].

Pain significantly affects patients' quality of daily life; therefore, patients often live in fear of the next pain attack and its severity. This condition frequently leads to severe anxiety and depressive disorders [4].

The pain syndrome is explained by several theories. Previously, it was believed that compression occurs mainly at the point where trigeminal nerve branches exit the brainstem. However, experimental studies have demonstrated that vascular compression also plays a significant role. In rare cases, aneurysms, arteriovenous malformations, tumors, cysts, or traumatic injuries may be causative factors. Short-term nerve compression is often painless, whereas prolonged compression leads to demyelination of the nerve, followed by possible axonal degeneration [10].

Patients with trigeminal neuralgia are often misdiagnosed. Initially, they usually seek medical care from dentists or otolaryngologists, and only after ineffective treatment do they consult neurologists. In some cases, unnecessary tooth extractions are performed. Early diagnosis significantly increases the effectiveness of treatment [8,9].

Analyzing the clinical course of trigeminal neuralgia based on electroneuromyographic parameters, genetic predisposition, and immune disorders, as well as developing an optimal treatment algorithm, remains one of the insufficiently studied issues in modern medicine, particularly among the Uzbek population. A comprehensive investigation of these aspects will contribute to improving the medical, social, and economic effectiveness of trigeminal neuralgia management. Therefore, research in this field is considered relevant and necessary.

Aim of the Study. The aim of this study was to investigate the clinical and neurological characteristics of the disease and the intensity of pain in patients suffering from trigeminal neuralgia.

Materials and Methods. Clinical and neurological examinations were conducted on 200 patients diagnosed with trigeminal neuralgia who sought medical care at the Neurology Unit of the Zhondor District Medical Association (Bukhara Region) during 2024–2025.

The assessment was performed using a structured questionnaire and the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), developed in collaboration with the Head of the Department of Neurology at Bukhara State Medical Institute, DSc Professor D.T. Khodjieva. Changes in clinical and neurological parameters were systematically analyzed.

Results. Based on the literature, numerous risk factors are known to contribute to the development of trigeminal neuralgia (TN). In the present study, these risk factors were systematically investigated. For this purpose, patients were provided with a questionnaire aimed at identifying factors they associated with the onset of the disease.

Analysis of the etiological factors in patients with trigeminal neuralgia demonstrated that the idiopathic form of neuralgia predominated compared to other types. These findings are also illustrated in Figure 1.

In our study, idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia was observed in 46% of patients. This prevalence was 4.5 times higher than trigeminal neuralgia associated with vascular diseases, 18.4 times higher than post-herpetic trigeminal neuralgia, 7 times higher than trigeminal neuralgia following viral infections, and 1.5 times higher than cases related to dental procedures.

Vascular-related causes were identified in 10% of patients. In our study, no cases of trigeminal neuralgia developing after traumatic injury or acute infection were observed. Post-herpetic trigeminal neuralgia was detected in 2.5% of patients, while trigeminal neuralgia following viral infections was observed in 6.5% of cases.

Another frequently identified cause was dental procedures, which were associated with trigeminal neuralgia in 30% of patients. This factor ranked second after idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia and was 6 times more frequent than trigeminal neuralgia associated with diabetes mellitus, 4.6 times more frequent than post-viral trigeminal neuralgia, and 12 times more frequent than post-herpetic trigeminal neuralgia. Overall, 5% of patients associated the onset of the disease with diabetes mellitus.

Figure 1. Etiological factors of trigeminal neuralgia (%)

Analysis of the seasonal pattern of disease exacerbation showed that trigeminal neuralgia attacks occurred most frequently in spring. This was associated with seasonal changes, cooler weather conditions, and increased exposure to spring winds. The next most frequent seasons were winter and autumn.

In spring, disease exacerbation was observed in 41.5% of cases, which was 1.7 times higher than in winter (41.5% vs. 23.5%), 1.9 times higher than in autumn (41.5% vs. 21.5%), and 3 times higher than in summer (41.5% vs. 13.5%).

In winter, exacerbations accounted for 23.5% of cases and were associated with cold weather, representing a 1.7-fold increase compared to summer. In autumn, exacerbations occurred in 21.5% of cases, which was 1.6 times higher than in summer and was also linked to cooling weather conditions. The lowest frequency was observed in summer (13.5%), which was associated with the use of indoor cooling devices.

Analysis of triggering factors revealed that patients reported multiple stimuli capable of provoking trigeminal neuralgia attacks. These included washing the face, shaving, tooth brushing, touching the nasal area, applying cosmetics, laughing, and exposure to light wind. The distribution of these triggering factors is illustrated in Figure 2.

In our study, 60% of patients reported that trigeminal neuralgia (TN) attacks were triggered by exposure to light wind, which was three times more frequent than triggers such as shaving, touching the nasal area, or applying cosmetics. In addition, 57.5% of patients indicated that TN attacks occurred after washing, showing nearly the same prevalence as attacks triggered by light wind exposure.

The next most common trigger was tooth brushing, reported by 45% of patients, which was more than twice as frequent as shaving, touching the nasal area, or applying cosmetics. TN attacks during laughing were reported by 38.5% of patients, which was twice as frequent as attacks triggered by shaving or touching the nasal area. Attacks were triggered by applying cosmetics in 20.5% of patients, shaving in 19.5%, and touching the nasal area in 18% of cases.

Clinical Features of the Course of Trigeminal Neuralgia

When analyzing the clinical course of trigeminal neuralgia, the first aspect assessed was the side of involvement. Right-sided trigeminal neuralgia was observed more frequently than left-sided involvement. Bilateral involvement of the trigeminal nerve was rare. The distribution of laterality is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Factors triggering trigeminal neuralgia attacks

Figure 3. Laterality of trigeminal neuralgia involvement (%)

Involvement of the first and second branches (I–II) of the trigeminal nerve was observed at nearly equal frequencies on both sides. Isolated involvement of the second branch was 2.5 times more frequent on the right side compared to the left. Combined involvement of the second and third branches (II–III) was more frequently observed on the right side (19.5%) than on the left, whereas bilateral involvement was rare (0.5%). Isolated involvement of the third branch was also more common on the right side (12.5%), which was 2.3 times higher than on the left side. Combined involvement of all three branches (I–II–III) was relatively rare; however, it was observed 1.6 times more frequently on the left side compared to the right.

In our study, we also analyzed the daily recurrence of trigeminal neuralgia attacks. The results showed that the majority of patients reported experiencing recurrent attacks ranging from 3–5 episodes to up to 10 episodes per day. The distribution of attack frequency is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Frequency of trigeminal neuralgia attacks per day (%)

As shown in Figure 4, the daily recurrence of trigeminal neuralgia attacks was reported as 3–5 episodes per day in 29.5% of patients, while 30.5% of patients experienced up to 10 attacks per day. These frequencies were 1.5 times higher compared to patients who experienced 1–2 attacks per day or more than 10 attacks per day. The occurrence of attacks 1–2 times per day was reported by 21% of patients, whereas more than 10 attacks per day were reported by 19% of patients. Analysis of attack duration showed that the majority of patients reported attacks lasting 1–3 minutes. In our study, trigeminal neuralgia attacks lasted 1–3 minutes in 49.5% of patients. This was 4.5 times more frequent than attacks lasting longer than 3 minutes (11%) and 1.7 times more frequent than attacks lasting 30 seconds to 1 minute. The shortest attack duration (1–3 seconds) was observed in the smallest proportion of patients (10.5%). Autonomic changes were also assessed in patients with trigeminal neuralgia. The results showed that during attacks, facial flushing was observed in 39% of patients and tachycardia in 29.5%. Facial pallor was reported in 20.5% of patients, while bradycardia was observed in 11%. Tachycardia occurred 2.7 times more frequently than bradycardia, and facial flushing was observed 1.9 times more frequently than facial pallor during attacks.

Assessment of pain intensity in trigeminal neuralgia (Visual Analogue Scale)

Pain intensity in trigeminal neuralgia was assessed using the Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). The VAS is a measurement tool used to quantify subjective experiences such as pain intensity. Patients rated their pain on a 10-point scale, which makes the method simple, rapid, and suitable for clinical assessment of subjective symptoms. In our study, patients reported pain intensity starting from 5 points during attacks. Therefore, patients who rated their pain as 5–6–7 points were classified into Group 1, while those who rated their pain as 8–9–10 points were classified into Group 2. Comparative analysis was performed between these two groups. Based on VAS assessment, 58% of patients reported unbearable (severe) pain, whereas 42% reported moderate pain. Moderate pain was 1.4 times less frequent than severe pain.

Pain characteristics in trigeminal neuralgia varied among patients and included stabbing (shooting), burning, and dull pain. In our study, shooting (stabbing) pain was the most common, reported by 69% of patients. This was 2.6 times more frequent than burning pain and 14 times more frequent than dull pain. These findings are illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Characteristics of pain in patients with trigeminal neuralgia (%)

Burning pain ranked second after stabbing (shooting) pain and was observed five times more frequently than dull pain. Burning pain was reported by 26% of patients, whereas dull pain accounted for a small proportion (5%). Assessment of pain intensity in patients with trigeminal neuralgia showed that patients predominantly reported moderate and severe pain rather than mild pain. Moderate pain was reported by 42% of patients, while severe pain was reported by 58%. Severe pain was 1.4 times more frequent than moderate pain.

Conclusion. The analysis of the results obtained in this study allows the following conclusions to be drawn:

1. Among the etiological factors of trigeminal neuralgia, idiopathic trigeminal neuralgia and cases developing after various dental procedures were the most frequently observed.
2. Disease exacerbations occurred most commonly in the spring season and were associated with seasonal changes. The most frequent triggering factor was exposure to light wind, including drafts, cold air, air-conditioning systems, and fans. These factors contributed to cooling, tissue edema, and the development of tunnel syndrome, thereby provoking pain attacks.

3. In trigeminal neuralgia, facial pain attacks most commonly lasted from 1 to 3 minutes, with attack frequency ranging from 3–5 to up to 10 episodes per day. Severe pain predominated (58%) compared to moderate pain (42%). Stabbing (shooting) pain (69%) was the leading pain type, followed by burning pain (26%), while dull pain was the least frequent.

Primary Prevention

Primary prevention of trigeminal neuralgia involves identifying disease-related risk factors and implementing measures aimed at their elimination. The following preventive strategies should be considered:

- Presence of a positive family history of the disease
- Timely and effective treatment of viral and acute infectious diseases
- Adequate, timely, and complete treatment of otorhinolaryngological, dental, and ophthalmological disorders
- Early diagnosis and management of diseases associated with impaired cerebral and peripheral circulation

Effective implementation of these measures requires increased awareness, knowledge, and vigilance among primary healthcare physicians, as patients most often initially seek medical care at the primary level. Therefore, educational and explanatory efforts should primarily target primary care providers to enable early detection of the disease and timely referral to appropriate specialists.

In addition, patients should be informed about secondary preventive measures. This includes providing patients with adequate knowledge about the disease, identifying and avoiding factors that trigger pain attacks, and adopting strategies that help prolong remission periods. Triggering factors include laughing, speaking, facial hygiene procedures, tooth brushing, shaving, touching the face, applying cosmetics, exposure to light wind, and the use of cooling devices, among others.

Psychological factors such as emotional stress, negative mood, and nervous tension may also exacerbate pain attacks. Therefore, patients should be educated about appropriate measures to take during acute pain episodes.

Enhancing patients' understanding of trigeminal neuralgia contributes to improving their medical awareness, strengthening preventive strategies, improving quality of life, and encouraging timely medical consultation when new or worsening symptoms occur.

REFERENCES

1. Афанасьева Е. В. Невралгия тройничного нерва. Гос. образовательное учреждение высш. проф. образования "Ростовский гос. мед. ун-т Федерального агентства по здравоохранению и социальному развитию". Ростов-на-Дону, 2008.
2. Балязина Е.В. Особенности нейроваскулярного конфликта, предрасполагающие к развитию невралгического статуса. Саратовский научно-медицинский журнал. 2012. Т. 8. № 2. С. 278-283.
3. Балязина Е.В., Балязин В.А., Аксенов Д.П., Бинов И.М., Суханова О.П., Бондарева О.И., Исаханова Т.А. Имеют ли значение размеры выходных черепных отверстий ветвей тройничного нерва в патогенезе классической невралгии тройничного нерва? Сибирский медицинский журнал (Иркутск). 2015. Т. 132. № 1. С. 77-82.
4. Балязина Е.В. Терапия классической невралгии тройничного нерва. Медицинский Вестник Северного Кавказа. 2011. Т. 22. № 2. С. 39-41

5. Балязина Е.В., Тарнопольская О.В. Возрастные особенности клиники классической невралгии тройничного нерва. Неврологический журнал. 2011. Т. 16. № 4. С. 39-44.
6. Балязина Е.В., Анатомические Предпосылки Преимущественно Правосторонней локализации болей у больных идиопатической невралгией тройничного нерва// Владикавказский Медико-Биологический Вестник. 2011. Т. Хiii. № 20-21. С. 110-115.
7. Балязина Е.В., Этиология и патогенез невралгии тройничного нерва Неврологический журнал. 2012. Т. 17. № 4. С. 4-12.
8. Джон Брильман, Скотт Коэн. Неврология. — МЕДпресс-информ, 2007. — С. 226. — (In a Page). — 2000 экз. — ISBN 5-98322-264-3
9. Bendtsen L, Zakrzewska JM, Heinskou TB, Hodaie M, Leal PRL, Nurmikko T, et al. Advances in diagnosis, classification, pathophysiology, and management of trigeminal neuralgia. *Lancet Neurol.* 2020;19 :784–96.
10. Rotshenker S. Wallerian degeneration: the innate-immune response to traumatic nerve injury. *Journal of Neuroinflammation.* 2011;8(1):109. doi:10.1186/1742-2094-8-109